

Virtual Try-On Application leveraging RoCE in Low-latency Edge Computing Networks

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ABSTRACT

Direct memory access (RDMA) over Converged Ethernet (RoCE) allows for direct memory transfers between systems, granting minimal latency and CPU overhead. This allows low-latency applications where data collection, analytics and feedback to the user are distributed between different nodes, optimizing resource management. RoCE, originally designed for data center operations, has the potential to effectively support applications deployed on edge nodes, where limited resources are available and low latency is required. This demo shows the use of RoCE in support to an AI-based application for smart shopping, deployed at the edge.

Keywords: Edge computing, RDMA over Converged Ethernet, Low-latency networking, virtual-try on application, smart shopping

1. OVERVIEW

Data transmission is traditionally performed through Transmission Control Protocol (TCP), being a reliable and ordered data delivery system. TCP assures the data integrity and flow control by establishing connections, acknowledging reception of data packets, and retransmitting lost packets if required [1]. TCP operates at a high level of abstraction, using connection-oriented communication, resulting in higher latency and CPU utilization due to protocol overhead. On the other hand, the introduction of RDMA is radically changing the way data transfer is performed, due to its reduced latency and faster data transfer rates. RDMA utilizes direct memory access from the memory of one hardware component into that of another without involving either one's operating system. The capability of RDMA is even more beneficial when it is employed in edge computing scenarios, with limited hardware resources and when it is paired with Data Processing Units (DPUs), designed to accelerate and offload tasks that were traditionally handled by CPU cores.

Low latency granted by RDMA allows for real-time data transmission and applications where resources are dislocated between multiple hardware components. RDMA over TCP performances have been discussed in previous literature [2] but how this design choice may affect the overall performance of an underlying application and affect the final user experience may require further analysis as it heavily depends on the specific application scenario. This demonstration takes an example application, deployed at the edge and exploiting RDMA communication.

The demonstration is deployed in a distributed federated testbed encompassing the CNIT/SSSA (ARNO testbed) located in Pisa, Italy and it presents preliminary results on RoCE efficiency in transmission activities when supporting an application with real-time requirements.

2. INNOVATION

In this demonstration, we aim to test RoCE-based communication [3] applied to an AI-based application, demonstrating its potential in granting low-latency and efficiency when in-network data transfer is required between nodes at the edge. The demonstration will show the effects of RoCE over TCP data transfer on latency when using distributed applications.

Edge computing brings resources closer to the user, reducing latency and bandwidth usage while also facing major constraints in terms of computational power [4]. Thus, the employment of distributed, modular resources represents a design choice to optimize the edge nodes capabilities maintaining their agility with respect to cloud servers and databases. When distributed resources are employed on the same application, communication between nodes must use proper protocols able to grant perceived low latency to the user. RoCE-based communication represents, then, a powerful tool for application deployment for edge computing scenarios.

This demonstration is designed to show the potential of an innovative solution in network intelligence and resources management. The chosen application provides direct feedback to the final user and represents an example for which latency has an important role for the user experience. The application, leverages on AI-based algorithms: the possibility to split its computational burden blocks between the nodes of the networks allows for

a more efficient usage of computational resources while still being able to communicate efficiently through RoCE. This will enable end-to-end guaranteed delays and a better exploitation of overall network resources.

3. DEMO CONTENT & IMPLEMENTATION

A. Goals

The main goal of the demonstration is to show a preliminary service-oriented end-to-end application, distributed between various network segments. This involves a node responsible for data collection and pre-processing and one or more other nodes employed on the actual application, aimed to provide low latency feedback to the user.

The chosen application is aimed to collect images through a camera and perform AI-based detection and processing, producing output images for the user, as better detailed in section C; it exploits the available GPU to obtain better performances in data processing, leveraging on specific libraries. The network exploits RoCE-based communication between its nodes to achieve fast communication.

The demonstration aims to highlight the advantages of adopting RoCE over TCP communication, especially when perceived low latency is important for the user experience.

B. Testbed setup and RoCE performances tests

The testbed to perform the experiments included two Dell Power Edge R760 servers (Intel Xeon Gold 6438Y+ CPU with 128 cores, 256 GB RAM, Ubuntu Linux with low latency kernel v5.15), equipped with Nvidia Bluefield 2 Data Processing Units (DPU). A D-Link DCS-4703E Ip camera is routed to one of these servers (Node 1) and provides the input parameters for the application detailed in the next section. The two DPUs are connected through Ethernet, allowing RoCE communication.

Figure 1: testbed setup, including a) Dell R760 servers and b) D-Link DCS-4703E cameras.

Node 1 is then dedicated to data collection and pre-processing, while the second server (Node 2) performs the main portion of the application and produces an output to be shown to the user. The two nodes are supposed to communicate at each iteration of the application as both perform a portion of the whole process: thus, it is important to grant low latency in communication between Node 1 and Node 2. Nodes can communicate through TCP or RoCE protocols. TCP utilizes adaptive flow mechanism to manage the data transmission between sender and the receiver and dynamically modifies the window size depending on the network conditions. TCP's sliding window mechanism allows it to utilize the network resources without the need for adjustments of buffer size.

On the other hand, RDMA operates at a lower level of networking stack, allowing direct memory access. The mechanism bypasses the traditional kernel buffer management; thus, the size and management of application buffers directly impacts its performances.

We conducted tests with multiple file sizes. Preliminary results, confirmed by previous literature [5], show that RoCE (Write mode) performs better than traditional TCP at any file size, determining lower latency (see *Figure 2*).

Similarly, smaller buffer sizes reduce latency due to faster data transmission, but they also determine higher frequency of the operations, which is why some tests have been performed to properly tailor the RoCE protocol to the deployed application.

Figure 2: Latency comparison between RoCE read/write operations and TCP traditional transfer.

C. Application

The application provided with the demo is summarized in *Figure 3*. It is a virtual-try on application, allowing the user to virtually try different pieces of clothing through a camera and a screen, working as a mirror. This application may find its employment for online shopping or in reducing lines in stores, while at the same time improving the whole shopping experience for the user. Low latency is a key aspect of the application.

The application, in its preliminary version, leverages a combination of existing libraries. Regarding Node 1 processing, person detection and the subsequent pose estimation are performed through Openpose [6] [7], a real-time system able to jointly detect human body and its keypoints (up to 135 keypoints) and areas. Openpose is designed to exploit GPU-base processing and represents a feasible choice for low latency applications.

The second portion of the application runs on Node 2 and consists in the virtual-try on. It collects the image of the user, its estimated pose and uses this information to produce a new image, with the user wearing a specific piece of clothing. The body pose is used to map users' body parts and warp the target piece clothing on them.

Figure 3: Flowchart of the application.

The second portion of the application exploits an existing image-based Virtual Try-On Network (VITON) [8]. Given a reference image with a clothed person and a target clothing item, the application synthesizes a new image where the target clothing is transferred naturally onto the corresponding region of the same person, whose body parts and pose information are preserved. Thus, the results are reported to the user through a screen, functioning as a virtual mirror. The application utilizes an environment based on Linux.

D. Implementation

The scenario of the demo is depicted in *Figure 4*. The demo employed two servers (Node 1 and Node 2) to deploy two separate AI-based applications (namely Openpose and VITON) and grant low CPU usage. Communication between Node 1 and Node 2 can be performed with RoCE or TCP protocols and it is intended to grant images streaming from one node to the other. The choice between RoCE and TCP is made available for the user during the demonstration, to evaluate its impact on the overall user experience.

Both RoCE and TCP transfer operations provide accurate timestamps to assess latency and report information about transferred file size, buffer size and network resources usage. Node 1 collects users input parameters, such as their image from the Ip camera, the piece of clothing to be tried and which type of communication protocol to use. Then, it performs person detection and pose estimation and sends the enhanced data to Node 2.

Node 2 is responsible for the merging the selected piece of clothing on the users' images and report the output to a screen, making the function of a virtual mirror. On screen, information such as network resources usage, hardware usage and latency will be displayed to provide a direct assessment of the application performances.

Figure 4: Distributed virtual Try-on Application

E. Proposed workflow

The demo workflow aims at showing the effects of RoCE and TCP setup on an application performance when distributed resources at the edge are employed. During the demonstration, the application will be shown to the audience, provided with the possibility to be tested with real-time data, recorded on the spot.

The proposed demonstration will be made available for testing both with TCP and RoCE communications protocols, to show the differences in terms of latency these two protocols determine. The application will provide on-screen results for audiences both in terms of network parameters, such as latency or hardware usage and in terms of result images from the Virtual Try-On application.

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